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Failure prediction of injection-moulded short-fibre composites: characterisation and prediction from coupons to components

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Injection-moulded short-fibre composites

Advantages

- ⇒ Lightweight
- ⇒ Complex 3D geometries
- ⇒ Short manufacturing cycles
- ⇒ Automatic processing

Applications in automotive

Challenge: complex skin-core microstructure

Injection moulding

Cross-section

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Injection moulding

Cross-section

Fibre orientation tensor

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{bmatrix}$$

a_{11} : flow direction (high in skin)

a_{22} : transverse direction (high in core)

a_{33} : thickness direction

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Cross-section

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Effect of fibre orientation on tensile properties

State-of-the-art coupled process-structural simulation (coupled FEA)

Process simulation
(local fibre orientation)

Calibration of Digimat's
elastic-plastic material model

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Structural FE simulations coupled with process simulation (coupled FEA)

Assign unique mechanical properties to each integration point based on mapped fibre orientation tensor

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Structural FE simulations coupled with process simulation (coupled FEA)

Assign unique mechanical properties to each integration point based on mapped fibre orientation tensor

Coupled FEA with existing failure criteria for SFRPs

Existing failure criteria for SFRPs (i.e. Tsai-Hill) under-predict the failure load: they consider failure initiation only and neglect material's fracture toughness

Objectives

Develop a Finite-Element (FE) methodology to predict failure of injection-moulded short-fibre reinforced Polyamide 6.6 composites (PA66-GF50), by accounting for the material's progressive failure

Applying the developed FE methodology to automotive components

Developing a new FE methodology for failure prediction

Characterising material properties

Level 1: coupons (Gc characterisation by CT tests)

- ⇒ Clear effect of fibre orientation and environmental conditions
- ⇒ FE simulations with CZM showed excellent agreement not only the peak load but also the subsequent gradual load decrease

Level 2: subcomponents (developing FE methodology)

Cohesive zone modelling (CZM)

⇒ Assignment of cohesive elements (CE) to fracture plane

Assignment of properties based on fibre orientation in the component

⇒ $a_{11}=0.8$ (skin) and $a_{11}=0.2$ (core)

Level 2: subcomponents (developing FE methodology)

Cohesive zone modelling (CZM)

- Assignment of cohesive elements (CE) to fracture plane

Assignment of properties based on fibre orientation in the component

- $a_{xx}=0.8$ (skin) and $a_{xx}=0.2$ (core)

Extrapolation of material properties

- FEA (CZM) showed excellent agreement of maximum failure load (within 2.6%)

Level 3: components (application of the developed methodology)

⇒ FEA (CZM) showed excellent agreement of failure load (error: 2.1%)

Conclusions

Poster number: P039

FEA using CZM have been demonstrated to accurately predict the failure of injection-moulded PA66-GF50 components based on experimentally-measured fracture toughness

- Provide more confidence in the design of the components in industry
- Contribute to design lighter and more costly-effective components

Failure prediction of injection-moulded short-fibre composites: characterisation and prediction from coupons to components

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Advantages and applications
 Injection-moulded short-fibre composites (IM-SFRPs) are lightweight, allow for complex 3D geometries, and have short manufacturing cycles.

Skin-core microstructure
 Injection moulding flow creates complex microstructure that leads to anisotropic and heterogeneous mechanical properties and failure modes, which complicates the design of SFRP components. This complex microstructure can be predicted by process simulations (as second-order orientation tensor).

Environmental effects
 IM-SFRPs are stiffer and more ductile under hotter or wetter conditions. Wet conditions can be mimicked in dry specimens by increasing the testing temperature with the corresponding ΔT . This temperature-moisture equivalence has been established for modulus, but not for failure.

State-of-the-art simulations and failure criteria for SFRP
 State-of-the-art simulations use material models calibrated by experimental tensile stress-strain curves (modulus and strength), but not fracture toughness. Existing failure criteria for SFRPs (i.e. Tsai-Hill) under-predict the failure load; they consider failure initiation only and neglect the material's toughness.

Objective
 This work aims to develop a Finite-Element (FE) methodology to predict failure of injection-moulded short-fibre Fibre-reinforced Polyamide 66 composites (FRP-GF50), by accounting for the material's progressive failure.

Breakage tests (quasi-static)
 Engine mounts used in the automotive industry were tested. The sequence of failure events in the fracture plane was determined through radiography. Failure initiation (●) was ductile (stable). Propagation (○) was brittle (unstable).

Sequence of failure events in FE
 FE simulations used Cohesive Zone Modelling (CZM) at the fracture plane to simulate failure and damage. The FE simulation predicted damage initiation at the top-left corner, and propagation first towards the right and then downwards, showing a good agreement with the experimental observations.

Level 3: components
 Applying the developed methodology to automotive components. FEA (CZM) shows excellent agreement of failure load (error: 2.1%).

Accuracy of predicted failure load
 FE with CZM was more accurate than Tsai-Hill's criterion. Relative failure load from the tests and FE simulations.

Process simulation and mapping onto FE model
 The fibre orientation tensor fields produced by process simulations were mapped onto an FE model. The fracture surface, $\alpha_{11}^{(2)}=0.8$ and $\alpha_{22}^{(2)}=0.2$. Fibre orientation tensor field.

Modelling strategy
 Cohesive elements were assigned at the fracture plane in the FE model. The local fibre orientation (defined on cohesive properties) was estimated by extrapolating properties to $\alpha_{11}^{(2)}=0.8$ and $\alpha_{22}^{(2)}=0.2$, and applied through partitions. An elastic-plastic material model was calibrated using dog-bone coupon testing data.

Breakage tests (quasi-static)
 Subcomponents representing automotive engine mounts were tested under different temperatures, and moisture conditions: Dry Air Humidity (DAH) and 80% Relative Humidity (RH80), with a corresponding ΔT of $\Delta T = 45^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature-moisture equivalence was verified in two pairs of conditions, where a moisture increase was accompanied by a ΔT (temperature decrease): Pair-A: $\alpha_{11}^{(2)}=0.8$ and $\alpha_{22}^{(2)}=0.2$; Pair-B: $\alpha_{11}^{(2)}=0.8$ and $\alpha_{22}^{(2)}=0.2$.

Fractography at the crack initiation point
 A crack initiated under the indenter at the bottom skin, and propagated along the top plane. Similar damage mechanisms were found within Pair-A and Pair-B. This shows that the temperature-moisture equivalence is also valid for failure, and at the subcomponent level.

Level 2: subcomponents
 Developing a new methodology for failure prediction. FEA (CZM) shows excellent agreement of failure load (error: within 2.6%).

Level 1: coupons [1]
 Characterising material properties. Experimentally-measured fracture toughness can be effectively used in FE simulations with CZM to predict not only the peak load but also the subsequent gradual load decrease.

Double specimens' tensile tests
 The tensile properties of PA66-GF50 were measured along 6 directions (corresponding to different orientation tensors α_{ij}). Each temperature-moisture equivalent pair (Pairs A & B) showed consistent properties within the pair.

Fracture toughness (critical strain energy release rate)
 Compact tension specimens were designed to measure the toughness of PA66-GF50 under different environmental conditions and fibre orientations. Two different data reduction methods were used, based on compliance calibration and J-integral. They both lead to consistent propagation toughnesses. The propagation toughness (G_{prop}) was at least 80% higher than initiation (G_{init}). The temperature-moisture equivalent Pairs A & B showed consistent toughnesses.

FE using Cohesive Zone Modelling (CZM)
 Cohesive laws were calibrated using the measured fracture toughness (G_{prop} and G_{init}). A trilinear law was required to predict both the peak load and the work of fracture.

Conclusions
 PA66-GF50 composite coupons, subcomponents and components were investigated under different environmental conditions. The work demonstrates that accounting for the finite fracture toughness of IM-SFRPs is required to accurately predict the industrial design of damage-tolerant and energy-absorbing automotive components.

Contributions
 Coupled process/structural simulations using CZM calibrated with measured fracture toughness showed excellent agreement of failure loads and sequence of events, compared to experimental results. This work provides the first characterisation of the fracture toughness of IM-SFRPs under the combined effect of fibre orientation, moisture level, and temperature. Temperature-moisture equivalence was verified not only for the modulus but also the failure strength and toughness in the Level 1, and subcomponent behaviour in Level 2.

Find out more!
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[1] Fujita et al. *Injection moulding process simulation of injection-moulded short-fibre composites under different environmental conditions*. *Compos Sci Technol*, 2023.